

A Collaborative Approach to Building a Hospital-Centered OMOP Data Layer for Clinically Meaningful ML/AI Applications in Sepsis

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AI-ready OMOP data = data model + operational guidance

Modified Study-a-thon approach documented in public OSF Project

- 1: Expert Preparation
- 2: Operational Workshop
- 3: Implementation

Hospital Test Beds:

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